

ATM 26: Airway Tree Modeling for Endobronchial Surgery: Structured description of the challenge design

CHALLENGE ORGANIZATION

Title

Use the title to convey the essential information on the challenge mission.

ATM 26: Airway Tree Modeling for Endobronchial Surgery

Challenge acronym

Preferable, provide a short acronym of the challenge (if any).

ATM26

Challenge abstract

Provide a summary of the challenge purpose. This should include a general introduction in the topic from both a biomedical as well as from a technical point of view and clearly state the envisioned technical and/or biomedical impact of the challenge.

Building on the success of the Airway Tree Modeling 2022 (ATM'22) challenge, which focused on binary segmentation of the tracheobronchial tree, we propose a new grand challenge for endobronchial intervention planning and navigation that more directly reflects the clinical demands of robot-assisted bronchoscopy and peripheral lung lesion biopsy. Clinically, accurate pre-operative airway modeling and intra-operative localization are critical for safely reaching small, peripheral nodules, reducing procedure time, and improving diagnostic yield in lung cancer and other pulmonary diseases. However, binary airway masks alone are insufficient for path planning, instrument targeting, and real-time guidance in complex, patient-specific bronchial trees. Technically, this challenge aims to advance the community from global airway detection towards fine-grained, anatomically consistent models and vision-based navigation, bridging pre-operative CT and intra-operative bronchoscopy. The proposed grand challenge will therefore consist of three sub-tasks: (i) an airway segmentation task similar to ATM'22, providing high-quality reference masks to enable robust benchmarking and continuity with prior work; (ii) a branch-wise labeling task, in which participants must assign standardized anatomical labels to each airway segment and produce a structured airway graph, supporting automated route planning, target localization, and reporting; and (iii) an endoscopic landmark recognition task, in which participants estimate the branch-wise position of the bronchoscope tip from monocular bronchoscopic images (and optionally CT priors), reflecting the core difficulty of vision-based navigation in deformable, low-texture lumens. The challenge will provide anonymized chest CT datasets with expert airway annotations and standardized branch nomenclature, and frame-based anatomical landmark labels. Participants may enter any subset of tasks. Quantitative evaluation will include overlap- and topology-based metrics for segmentation, label accuracy and tree-consistency scores for branch naming, and classification accuracy of landmark recognition. . Through this design, the challenge aims to catalyze clinically meaningful advances in endobronchial planning and navigation, and to benchmark emerging methods under a realistic, multi-task setting.

Challenge keywords

List the primary keywords that characterize the challenge.

Endobronchial Intervention, Airway Tree, Surgical Autonomy

Year

2026

Novelty of the challenge

Briefly describe the novelty of the challenge.

Building on the success of the Airway Tree Modeling 2022 (ATM'22) challenge, which focused on binary segmentation of the tracheobronchial tree, we propose a new grand challenge for endobronchial intervention planning and navigation. The main difference is that ATM22 focuses only on binary segmentation while ATM26 covers the full stages of pre-operative planning and intra-operative navigation with multi-class fine-grained labels.

Task description and application scenarios

Briefly describe the application scenarios for the tasks in the challenge.

ATM26 aims at the endobronchial intervention planning and navigation. This can be applied to peripheral nodule biopsy since these tasks can provide the map as guidance.

FURTHER INFORMATION FOR CONFERENCE ORGANIZERS

Workshop

If the challenge is part of a workshop, please indicate the workshop.

Current not determined. We are also applying the workshop of Endoluminal Intervention Navigation and Autonomy (EndoLINA) in MICCAI 26. If both proposals are accepted, we prefer to a merged event.

Duration

How long does the challenge take?

2 Hours

In case you selected half or full day, please explain why you need a long slot for your challenge.

N/A

Expected number of participants

Please explain the basis of your estimate (e.g. numbers from previous challenges) and/or provide a list of potential participants and indicate if they have already confirmed their willingness to contribute.

According to ATM22 challenge, the expected number of teams which will participate all phases of the challenge is at least 30. There are also active submissions from multiple institutes. Please refer to the Long-Term leaderboard of ATM22. Potential teams including:

- Royal Brompton Hospital, Imperial College London, UK
- Shanghai AI Lab, China

- DAMO Academy, USA
- The University of New South Wales, Australia
- InferVision Co., Ltd, China
- Harvard Medical School, Boston, USA

...

Publication and future plans

Please indicate if you plan to coordinate a publication of the challenge results.

We plan to submit to IEEE TMI/MedIA/Nature/Science/NEJM family journals.

MICCAI LNCS proceedings

Indicate if you want to offer MICCAI Springer LNCS proceedings to the participants. Publishing a proceedings volume is optional and at the discretion of each challenge's organizers. At a minimum, organizers must ensure that a description of each participant's submission is publicly available. Organizers who wish to publish MICCAI Springer LNCS proceedings must adhere to the MICCAI Satellite events publication process.

No

Collaboration with European Society of Radiology (ESR)

In collaboration with European Society of Radiology (ESR), we announce special clinical interest topics with associated clinicians who can help with the preparation of the proposals; the best 3 challenge proposals on these topics will get the opportunity to present their challenges at the European Congress of Radiology (ECR) 2027 in a special session. If you want to organize a challenge in collaboration with ESR on one of these topics, please reach out to the MICCAI Challenges Team (miccai-challenges-2026@dkfz-heidelberg.de) and we will put you in contact with the corresponding clinician.

Challenge in collaboration with ESR. Ticking 'Yes' implies that the challenge has been prepared in collaboration with the clinical contact point.

No

Space and hardware requirements

Organizers of on-site challenges must provide a fair computing environment for all participants. For instance, algorithms should run on the same computing platform provided to all.

projectors and monitors.

TASK 1: Binary Airway Segmentation

SUMMARY

Abstract

Provide a summary of the challenge purpose. This should include a general introduction in the topic from both a biomedical as well as from a technical point of view and clearly state the envisioned technical and/or biomedical impact of the challenge.

ATM26 Task 1 benchmarks topologypreserving airway tree segmentation from chest CT. The goal is a connected airway lumen/tree from trachea to distal bronchi under multivendor acquisition and diverse protocols. The evaluation emphasizes both overlap accuracy and structural completeness to support intervention planning and downstream navigation.

Keywords

List the primary keywords that characterize the task.

airway segmentation, chest CT, topology metrics, distal bronchi, robustness

ORGANIZATION

Organizers

a) Provide information on the organizing team (names and affiliations).

Institute of Medical Robotics, Shanghai Jiao Tong University

Yun Gu, Minghui Zhang, Junyang Wu, Hanxiao Zhang, Yaoyu Liu, Chenyu Li, Jie Yang, Guang-Zhong Yang

Shanghai Chest Hospital

Fangfang Xie, Chunxi Zhang, Jiayuan Sun

Imperial College London

Guang Yang

Medical Image Insights

Pengcheng Shi, Xinglin Zhang

b) Provide information on the primary contact person.

Yun Gu (yungu@ieee.org), Minghui Zhang (minghuizhang@sjtu.edu.cn)

c) Indicate whether clinicians are part of the organizing team. If yes, describe their role.

Yes, the clinicians are part of the organization team. They are from Shanghai Chest Hospital clinical team for task definition, annotation protocol and review.

Life cycle type

Define the intended submission cycle of the challenge. Include information on whether/how the challenge will be continued after the challenge has taken place. Not every challenge closes after the submission deadline (one-time

event). Sometimes it is possible to submit results after the deadline (open call) or the challenge is repeated with some modifications (repeated event).

Examples:

- One-time event with fixed conference submission deadline
- Open call (challenge opens for new submissions after conference deadline)
- Repeated event with annual fixed conference submission deadline

Repeated event with annual fixed conference submission deadline

Challenge venue and platform

a) Report the event (e.g. conference) that is associated with the challenge (if any).

MICCAI 2026

b) Report the platform used to run the challenge.

grand-challenge.org

c) Do you agree that the your submission is shared with the platform (e.g., grand-challenge, synapse...) that you indicated?

Please note: 1) this purpose of such sharing is that the challenge chairs and the platform can communicate smoothly, your answer won't impact the review of your proposal; 2) regardless of your response to this question, it is your responsibility to perform all actions required by the platform (e.g. filling their submission request).

Yes

d) Provide the URL for the challenge website (if any).

<https://atm26.grand-challenge.org/> (to appear)

Participation policies

a) Define the allowed user interaction of the algorithms assessed. This includes the policy regarding any curation, (pre-)processing and (pre-)training steps.

Fully automatic inference only; no manual correction on test.

b) Define the policy on the usage of training data. The data used to train algorithms may, for example, be restricted to the data provided by the challenge or may also include publicly available data including (open) pre-trained nets. Clarify whether such additional data needs to be publicly available at the time of the challenge launch. Clarify whether adding (private) annotations of the public data is allowed.

During the challenge: train on provided CT training set only.

After the challenge: allow public CT/pretraining with full disclosure and license compliance.

c) Define the participation policy for members of the organizers' institutes. For example, members of the organizers' institutes may participate in the challenge but are not eligible for awards.

May participate but not eligible for awards and not listed in leaderboard

d) Define the award policy. In particular, provide details with respect to challenge prizes.

best overall Task 1; best robustness subset performance (e.g., large-spacing / low-quality).

e) Define the policy for result announcement.

Examples:

- Top 3 performing methods will be announced publicly.
- Participating teams can choose whether the performance results will be made public.

Public final leaderboard; top teams announced at MICCAI.

f) Define the publication policy. In particular, provide details on ...

- ... who of the participating teams/the participating teams' members qualifies as author
- ... whether the participating teams may publish their own results separately, and (if so)
- ... whether an embargo time is defined (so that challenge organizers can publish a challenge paper first).

Organizers publish challenge summary for this task (dataset, metrics, results). Top teams invited as co-authors contingent on timely method write-up and reproducibility container.

Submission method

a) Describe the method used for result submission. Preferably, provide a link to the submission instructions.

Examples:

- Docker container on the Synapse platform. Link to submission instructions: <URL>
- Algorithm output was sent to organizers via e-mail. Submission instructions were sent by e-mail.

Docker container submission. Input: CT volume. Output: airway binary mask (NIfTI) and optional probability map. Orientation/spacing conventions strictly enforced.

b) Provide information on the possibility for participating teams to evaluate their algorithms before submitting final results. For example, many challenges allow submission of multiple results, and only the last run is officially counted to compute challenge results.

Yes. Validation evaluation server with submission limits; local evaluation kit provided. The validation platform is a docker with RTX3090 GPU (24GB VRAM).

Challenge schedule

Provide a timetable for the challenge. Preferably, this should include

- the release date(s) of the training cases (if any)
- the registration date/period
- the release date(s) of the test cases and validation cases (if any)
- the submission date(s)
- associated workshop days (if any)
- the release date(s) of the results

1 May 2026: Registration Open.

15 May 2026: Release of the training and validation data.

25 Aug 2026: Deadline for validation submission and Testing set opening

15 Sep 2026: Deadline for testing submission

4 Oct 2026: The top 10 teams and results have been announced in the workshop

Ethics approval

Indicate whether ethics approval is necessary for the data. If yes, provide details on the ethics approval, preferably institutional review board, location, date and number of the ethics approval (if applicable). Add the URL or a reference to the document of the ethics approval (if available).

Shanghai Chest Hospital

Institutional review board: SHANGHAI CHEST HOSPITAL

Location: SHANGHAI

Date: 2021/09/17

Number: KS(Y)21328

Data usage agreement

Clarify how the data can be used and distributed by the teams that participate in the challenge and by others during and after the challenge. This should include the explicit listing of the license applied.

Examples:

- CC BY (Attribution)
- CC BY-SA (Attribution-ShareAlike)
- CC BY-ND (Attribution-NoDerivs)
- CC BY-NC (Attribution-NonCommercial)
- CC BY-NC-SA (Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike)
- CC BY-NC-ND (Attribution-NonCommercial-NoDerivs)

Please note that the data license should not differ among sources. In case a license has to be changed, it has to be reported to the MICCAI challenges team and changed in the proposal.

CC BY-NC-SA (Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike)

Code availability

a) Provide information on the accessibility of the organizers' evaluation software (e.g. code to produce rankings). Preferably, provide a link to the code and add information on the supported platforms.

If this challenge is accepted, we will immediately release our ranking code on Github and provide the link. The repo will follow the similar style of ATM22 at

<https://github.com/EndoluminalSurgicalVision-IMR/ATM-22-Related-Work>

b) In an analogous manner, provide information on the accessibility of the participating teams' code.

The top five teams are required to submit their algorithms via Docker and open-source code.

Conflicts of interest

Provide information related to conflicts of interest. In particular provide information related to sponsoring/funding of the challenge. Also, state explicitly who had/will have access to the test case labels and when.

The members from the Insitute of Medical Robotics, Shanghai Jiao Tong University, and Shanghai Chest hospital will have access to the test case labels during the challenge procedure.

MISSION OF THE CHALLENGE

Field(s) of application

State the main field(s) of application that the participating algorithms target.

Examples:

- Diagnosis
- Education
- Intervention assistance
- Intervention follow-up
- Intervention planning
- Prognosis
- Research
- Screening
- Training
- Cross-phase

CAD, Intervention planning

Task category(ies)

State the task category(ies)

Examples:

- Classification
- Detection
- Localization
- Modeling
- Prediction
- Reconstruction
- Registration
- Retrieval

- Segmentation
- Tracking

Segmentation

Cohorts

We distinguish between the target cohort and the challenge cohort. For example, a challenge could be designed around the task of medical instrument tracking in robotic kidney surgery. While the challenge could be based on ex vivo data obtained from a laparoscopic training environment with porcine organs (challenge cohort), the final biomedical application (i.e. robotic kidney surgery) would be targeted on real patients with certain characteristics defined by inclusion criteria such as restrictions regarding sex or age (target cohort).

a) Describe the target cohort, i.e. the subjects/objects from whom/which the data would be acquired in the final biomedical application.

The final biomedical application would be targeted at real patients with respiratory diseases.

b) Describe the challenge cohort, i.e. the subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the challenge data was acquired.

1. LIDC dataset of which the z-axis thickness smaller than 0.7mm;
2. Samples from Shanghai Chest Hospital from 400 patients who underwent the CT imaging during 2019.1 and 2020.1.

Imaging modality(ies)

Specify the imaging technique(s) applied in the challenge.

Computed Tomography (CT)

Context information

Provide additional information given along with the images. The information may correspond ...

a) ... directly to the image data (e.g. tumor volume).

None.

b) ... to the patient in general (e.g. sex, medical history).

Age (Adult/Child).

Target entity(ies)

a) Describe the data origin, i.e. the region(s)/part(s) of subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the image data would be acquired in the final biomedical application (e.g. brain shown in computed tomography (CT) data, abdomen shown in laparoscopic video data, operating room shown in video data, thorax shown in fluoroscopy video). If necessary, differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

Lung shown in Thoracic CT scans.

b) Describe the algorithm target, i.e. the structure(s)/subject(s)/object(s)/component(s) that the participating algorithms have been designed to focus on (e.g. tumor in the brain, tip of a medical instrument, nurse in an operating theater, catheter in a fluoroscopy scan). If necessary, differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

The airway in the Lung, including the trachea, main bronchi, lobar bronchi, and distal segmental bronchi.

Assessment aim(s)

Identify the property(ies) of the algorithms to be optimized to perform well in the challenge. If multiple properties are assessed, prioritize them (if appropriate). The properties should then be reflected in the metrics applied (see below, parameter metric(s)), and the priorities should be reflected in the ranking when combining multiple metrics that assess different properties.

- Example 1: Find highly accurate liver segmentation algorithm for CT images.
- Example 2: Find lung tumor detection algorithm with high sensitivity and specificity for mammography images.

Corresponding metrics are listed below (parameter metric(s)).

Consistency, Accuracy

DATA SETS

Data source(s)

a) Specify the device(s) used to acquire the challenge data. This includes details on the device(s) used to acquire the imaging data (e.g. manufacturer) as well as information on additional devices used for performance assessment (e.g. tracking system used in a surgical setting).

Siemens Definition, Emotion, and Sensation scanner.

b) Describe relevant details on the imaging process/data acquisition for each acquisition device (e.g. image acquisition protocol(s)).

The thoracic CT scans are acquired under the protocol of Digital Imaging and Communications in Medicine (DICOM). The manual delineation of the airway is saved as the Neuroimaging Informatics Technology Initiative (NIFTI).

c) Specify the center(s)/institute(s) in which the data was acquired and/or the data providing platform/source (e.g. previous challenge). If this information is not provided (e.g. for anonymization reasons), specify why.

Same as ATM22.

[1] The thoracic CT scans of the BAS dataset are selected from the LIDC-IDRI dataset.

[2] Shanghai Chest Hospital

d) Describe relevant characteristics (e.g. level of expertise) of the subjects (e.g. surgeon)/objects (e.g. robot) involved in the data acquisition process (if any).

Each thoracic CT scan is first preprocessed by a strong deep learning model (Zheng et.al) to acquire the preliminary segmentation result and then delineated and double-checked by three radiologists with more than five years of professional experience to acquire the final refined airway tree structure.

Zheng H, Qin Y, Gu Y, et al. Alleviating Class-wise Gradient Imbalance for Pulmonary Airway Segmentation. IEEE Transactions on Medical Imaging, 2021.

Training and test case characteristics

a) State what is meant by one case in this challenge. A case encompasses all data that is processed to produce one result that is compared to the corresponding reference result (i.e. the desired algorithm output).

Examples:

- Training and test cases both represent a CT image of a human brain. Training cases have a weak annotation (tumor present or not and tumor volume (if any)) while the test cases are annotated with the tumor contour (if any).
- A case refers to all information that is available for one particular patient in a specific study. This information always includes the image information as specified in data source(s) (see above) and may include context information (see above). Both training and test cases are annotated with survival (binary) 5 years after (first) image was taken.

Training and test cases both represent a CT image of a human chest, They all have a full annotation of the airway tree structure.

b) State the total number of training, validation and test cases.

Same as ATM22.

The training dataset contains 300 CT scans, which are generally with the z-axis spacing smaller than 0.7mm and the quality of imaging is good without lesions. The test dataset contains 150 CT scans that can be categorized into three parts. The first part includes 100 CT scans generally with good image quality (z-axis spacing smaller than 0.7mm). The second part includes 30 CT scans that share large z-axis spacing. The third part contains 20 CT scans with low quality (e.g., with COVID-19 lesion). The second and the third parts correspond to these two tracks respectively, through which we can measure the robustness and the generalization ability of the automatic airway segmentation algorithms.

c) How much of the data are already annotated (stratified by train test in percentage)?

Full.

d) Explain why a total number of cases and the specific proportion of training, validation and test cases was chosen.

In general, we split the dataset into training set, validation set, and test set by 6:1:3.

e) Mention further important characteristics of the training, validation and test cases (e.g. class distribution in classification tasks chosen according to real-world distribution vs. equal class distribution) and justify the choice.

We mainly focus on the spacing of CT scans in training/validation/testing part. In this dataset, the CT scans in training dataset are generally with the z-axis spacing smaller than 0.7mm, and the quality of imaging is good without lesions. In testing part, we will add more samples with large spacing and low quality.

f) Challenge organizers are encouraged to (partly) use unseen, unpublished data for their challenges. Describe if new data will be used for the challenge and state the number of cases along with the proportion of new data.

We use the same dataset as ATM22.

Annotation characteristics

a) Describe the method for determining the reference annotation, i.e. the desired algorithm output. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Possible methods include manual image

annotation, in silico ground truth generation and annotation by automatic methods.

If human annotation was involved, state the number of annotators.

The airway tree structure is manually annotated by three radiologists with more than five years of professional experience.

b) Provide the instructions given to the annotators (if any) prior to the annotation. This may include description of a training phase with the software. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Preferably, provide a link to the annotation protocol.

The radiologists used the ITK-SNAP software to generate the trachea by region growing methods and corrected the trachea. Then they delineated the bronchi branch-by-branch through backtracking methods.

c) Provide details on the subject(s)/algorithm(s) that annotated the cases (e.g. information on level of expertise such as number of years of professional experience, medically-trained or not). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

They are radiologists with more than five years of professional experience.

d) Describe the method(s) used to merge multiple annotations for one case (if any). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

The radiologists are first label the cases independently without any discussion. After that, the groundtruth is obtained by the majority voting and confirmed by the senior radiologist.

Data pre-processing method(s)

Describe the method(s) used for pre-processing the raw training data before it is provided to the participating teams. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

The original thoracic CT scans share a large input size, while the airway tree structure exists in the lung area, hence, we provided the lung area coordinate (3D bounding box information) of each sample for localization usage.

Sources of error

a) Describe the most relevant possible error sources related to the image annotation. If possible, estimate the magnitude (range) of these errors, using inter-and intra-annotator variability, for example. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases, if necessary.

Restricted to the slice thickness and x-y plane resolution of CT scans, the distal small bronchus is hard to distinguish from the image level. We promise that our radiologists have dealt with such hard segmentation areas together and incorporated their professional experience as prior knowledge.

b) In an analogous manner, describe and quantify other relevant sources of error.

None.

ASSESSMENT METHODS

Metric(s)

a) Define the metric(s) to assess a property of an algorithm. These metrics should reflect the desired algorithm properties described in assessment aim(s) (see above). State which metric(s) were used to compute the ranking(s) (if

any).

- Example 1: Dice Similarity Coefficient (DSC)
- Example 2: Area under curve (AUC)

[1] tree length detected rate (TLD) and the branches detected rate (BD).

[2] Dice similarity coefficient and cDice (Shit et.al)

[3] Betti-Error

Specifically, The TLD is the fraction detected correctly relative to the total tree length in the reference label, and the BD is the percentage of branches that are detected correctly with respect to the total number of branches present in the reference label. cDice is the skeleton-based Dice metric which only measures the Dice metric after the skelenisation of the prediction. Betti-Error measure the difference of betti-0 value (the number of connected components) between the prediction and groundtruth.

b) Justify why the metric(s) was/were chosen, preferably with reference to the biomedical application.

Same as ATM 22. We aim to segment the accurate airway tree model. For one thing, only the largest component of the binary airway segmentation results are of clinical use, to measure the completeness and the connectedness of the participating teams' results, we use the tree length detected rate (TD) and the branches detected rate (BD). For another thing, we use the metric of the Dice similarity coefficient to measure the overlap-wise segmentation accuracy. In addition, we use the F1 score to measure the voxel-wise segmentation performance, which takes into account both the false positive and false negative errors.

Ranking method(s)

a) Describe the method used to compute a performance rank for all submitted algorithms based on the generated metric results on the test cases. Typically the text will describe how results obtained per case and metric are aggregated to arrive at a final score/ranking. Ideally, provide the ranking scheme as a concrete pseudo code.

We will report the ranking of each metric and the mean position of each team considering all metrics.

b) Describe the method(s) used to manage submissions with missing results on test cases.

The standalone metrics are all suitable for this situation. If the submissions miss results, they will inevitably receive a low score.

c) Justify why the described ranking scheme(s) was/were used.

We consider the reasonable metrics involved in this task. Although previous works used the weighted score for ranking, we still prefer to the mean ranking position of each metrics as the final ranking. This is also widely used in recent challenges which can avoid the weighting issues and also achieves good agreements in our ATM22 without conflicts.

Statistical analyses

Provide an overview of the statistical approaches used in the scope of the challenge analysis. Details can be provided in the parameters below. For each parameter, justify why the described statistical method(s) was/were used and, if necessary, add a description of any method used to assess whether the data met the assumptions required for the particular statistical approach.

We will use the Kendall tau analysis and Wilcoxon signed-rank to quantify the agreement of two rankings (e.g. for two different metrics) and we will provide the boxplots to visualize the results.

Provide a description of how the precision of the performance estimates of individual algorithms is assessed (e.g. confidence interval of the mean on the test set computed using percentile bootstrap, confidence interval of the accuracy on the test set computed using percentile bootstrap).

We use the Kendall tau analysis and Wilcoxon signed-rank to quantify the robustness of a ranking and determine whether the automatic algorithms designed by the participants are robust or not under different methods.

Provide a description of how variability of the performance of individual algorithms across tests cases is assessed (e.g. SD across test cases, IQR, graphs, reporting outliers...).

Std and per-case distributions; distal vs proximal breakages; failure gallery.

Provide a description of how variability of rankings is assessed.

We will Bootstrap re-ranking and report rank stability and Kendall/Spearman correlations.

Provide a description of statistical tests that are used to assess whether the differences in performance between algorithms are statistically significant.

We use the Kendall tau analysis and Wilcoxon signed-rank to quantify the robustness of a ranking and determine whether the automatic algorithms designed by the participants are robust or not under different methods.

Provide a description of the missing data handling.

Missing predictions treated as failures and exclude excessive-missing methods from significance tests if needed.

Indicate any software product that is used for all data analysis methods.

No specific software. We will use python code to calculate the statistic values.

Further analyses

Present further analyses to be performed (if applicable), e.g. related to

- combining algorithms via ensembling,
- inter-algorithm variability,
- common problems/biases of the submitted methods, or
- ranking variability.

For the future possible benchmark/joint paper, we would like to evaluate the top 10 performing methods, analyzing the inter-algorithm variability and common problems/biases. We also plan to combine algorithms via ensembling to design the valuable algorithm for airway segmentation and clinical usage.

TASK 2: Branch-wise Anatomical Labeling

SUMMARY

Abstract

Provide a summary of the challenge purpose. This should include a general introduction in the topic from both a biomedical as well as from a technical point of view and clearly state the envisioned technical and/or biomedical impact of the challenge.

ATM26 Task 2 moves from binary segmentation to clinically structured airway modeling: participants output an anatomically consistent airway representation (multiclass label map and/or airway graph) with hierarchical branch naming (lobar/segmental/subsegmental). This enables trajectory planning, lesion to airway association, and standardized reporting while testing robustness to anatomical variants and label imbalance.

Keywords

List the primary keywords that characterize the task.

airway labeling, airway graph, hierarchical nomenclature, subsegmental branches, tree consistency

ORGANIZATION

Organizers

a) Provide information on the organizing team (names and affiliations).

Same as Task 1

b) Provide information on the primary contact person.

Yun Gu (yungu@ieee.org), Yaoyu Liu (lyyu19@sjtu.edu.cn)

c) Indicate whether clinicians are part of the organizing team. If yes, describe their role.

Same as Task 1.

Life cycle type

Define the intended submission cycle of the challenge. Include information on whether/how the challenge will be continued after the challenge has taken place. Not every challenge closes after the submission deadline (one-time event). Sometimes it is possible to submit results after the deadline (open call) or the challenge is repeated with some modifications (repeated event).

Examples:

- One-time event with fixed conference submission deadline
- Open call (challenge opens for new submissions after conference deadline)
- Repeated event with annual fixed conference submission deadline

Repeated event with annual fixed conference submission deadline

Challenge venue and platform

a) Report the event (e.g. conference) that is associated with the challenge (if any).

MICCAI 2026

b) Report the platform used to run the challenge.

grand-challenge.org

c) Do you agree that the your submission is shared with the platform (e.g., grand-challenge, synapse...) that you indicated?

Please note: 1) this purpose of such sharing is that the challenge chairs and the platform can communicate smoothly, your answer won't impact the review of your proposal; 2) regardless of your response to this question, it is your responsibility to perform all actions required by the platform (e.g. filling their submission request).

Yes

d) Provide the URL for the challenge website (if any).

<https://atm26.grand-challenge.org/> (to appear)

Participation policies

a) Define the allowed user interaction of the algorithms assessed. This includes the policy regarding any curation, (pre-)processing and (pre-)training steps.

Fully automatic inference only; no manual correction on test.

b) Define the policy on the usage of training data. The data used to train algorithms may, for example, be restricted to the data provided by the challenge or may also include publicly available data including (open) pre-trained nets. Clarify whether such additional data needs to be publicly available at the time of the challenge launch. Clarify whether adding (private) annotations of the public data is allowed.

Same as Task1.

c) Define the participation policy for members of the organizers' institutes. For example, members of the organizers' institutes may participate in the challenge but are not eligible for awards.

May participate but not eligible for awards and not listed in leaderboard

d) Define the award policy. In particular, provide details with respect to challenge prizes.

best overall Task 2

e) Define the policy for result announcement.

Examples:

- Top 3 performing methods will be announced publicly.
- Participating teams can choose whether the performance results will be made public.

Same as Task 1.

f) Define the publication policy. In particular, provide details on ...

- ... who of the participating teams/the participating teams' members qualifies as author

- ... whether the participating teams may publish their own results separately, and (if so)
- ... whether an embargo time is defined (so that challenge organizers can publish a challenge paper first).

Same as Task 1.

Submission method

a) Describe the method used for result submission. Preferably, provide a link to the submission instructions.

Examples:

- Docker container on the Synapse platform. Link to submission instructions: <URL>
- Algorithm output was sent to organizers via e-mail. Submission instructions were sent by e-mail.

Docker container submission. Input: CT volume. Output: multi-class label map (NIFTI) and/or airway graph JSON (nodes/edges, per-branch labels, confidence, parent-child structure).

b) Provide information on the possibility for participating teams to evaluate their algorithms before submitting final results. For example, many challenges allow submission of multiple results, and only the last run is officially counted to compute challenge results.

Yes. Validation evaluation server with submission limits; local evaluation kit provided. The validation platform is a docker with 2*RTX3090 GPU (48GB VRAM)

Challenge schedule

Provide a timetable for the challenge. Preferably, this should include

- the release date(s) of the training cases (if any)
- the registration date/period
- the release date(s) of the test cases and validation cases (if any)
- the submission date(s)
- associated workshop days (if any)
- the release date(s) of the results

Same as Task 1.

Ethics approval

Indicate whether ethics approval is necessary for the data. If yes, provide details on the ethics approval, preferably institutional review board, location, date and number of the ethics approval (if applicable). Add the URL or a reference to the document of the ethics approval (if available).

Same as Task 1.

Data usage agreement

Clarify how the data can be used and distributed by the teams that participate in the challenge and by others during and after the challenge. This should include the explicit listing of the license applied.

Examples:

- CC BY (Attribution)
- CC BY-SA (Attribution-ShareAlike)
- CC BY-ND (Attribution-NoDerivs)
- CC BY-NC (Attribution-NonCommercial)
- CC BY-NC-SA (Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike)
- CC BY-NC-ND (Attribution-NonCommercial-NoDerivs)

Please note that the data license should not differ among sources. In case a license has to be changed, it has to be reported to the MICCAI challenges team and changed in the proposal.

CC BY-NC-SA (Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike)

Code availability

a) Provide information on the accessibility of the organizers' evaluation software (e.g. code to produce rankings). Preferably, provide a link to the code and add information on the supported platforms.

Same as Task 1.

b) In an analogous manner, provide information on the accessibility of the participating teams' code.

Same as Task1.

Conflicts of interest

Provide information related to conflicts of interest. In particular provide information related to sponsoring/funding of the challenge. Also, state explicitly who had/will have access to the test case labels and when.

Same as Task 1.

MISSION OF THE CHALLENGE

Field(s) of application

State the main field(s) of application that the participating algorithms target.

Examples:

- Diagnosis
- Education
- Intervention assistance
- Intervention follow-up
- Intervention planning
- Prognosis
- Research

- Screening
- Training
- Cross-phase

CAD, Intervention planning

Task category(ies)

State the task category(ies)

Examples:

- Classification
- Detection
- Localization
- Modeling
- Prediction
- Reconstruction
- Registration
- Retrieval
- Segmentation
- Tracking

Segmentation, Classification

Cohorts

We distinguish between the target cohort and the challenge cohort. For example, a challenge could be designed around the task of medical instrument tracking in robotic kidney surgery. While the challenge could be based on ex vivo data obtained from a laparoscopic training environment with porcine organs (challenge cohort), the final biomedical application (i.e. robotic kidney surgery) would be targeted on real patients with certain characteristics defined by inclusion criteria such as restrictions regarding sex or age (target cohort).

a) Describe the target cohort, i.e. the subjects/objects from whom/which the data would be acquired in the final biomedical application.

Same as Task 1.

b) Describe the challenge cohort, i.e. the subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the challenge data was acquired.

1. LIDC dataset of which the z-axis thickness smaller than 0.7mm;
2. Samples from Shanghai Chest Hospital from 400 patients who underwent the CT imaging during 2019.1 and 2020.1.

Imaging modality(ies)

Specify the imaging technique(s) applied in the challenge.

Computed Tomography (CT)

Context information

Provide additional information given along with the images. The information may correspond ...

a) ... directly to the image data (e.g. tumor volume).

None.

b) ... to the patient in general (e.g. sex, medical history).

Same as Task 1.

Target entity(ies)

a) Describe the data origin, i.e. the region(s)/part(s) of subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the image data would be acquired in the final biomedical application (e.g. brain shown in computed tomography (CT) data, abdomen shown in laparoscopic video data, operating room shown in video data, thorax shown in fluoroscopy video). If necessary, differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

Lung shown in Thoracic CT scans.

b) Describe the algorithm target, i.e. the structure(s)/subject(s)/object(s)/component(s) that the participating algorithms have been designed to focus on (e.g. tumor in the brain, tip of a medical instrument, nurse in an operating theater, catheter in a fluoroscopy scan). If necessary, differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

Same as Task 1.

Assessment aim(s)

Identify the property(ies) of the algorithms to be optimized to perform well in the challenge. If multiple properties are assessed, prioritize them (if appropriate). The properties should then be reflected in the metrics applied (see below, parameter metric(s)), and the priorities should be reflected in the ranking when combining multiple metrics that assess different properties.

- Example 1: Find highly accurate liver segmentation algorithm for CT images.
- Example 2: Find lung tumor detection algorithm with high sensitivity and specificity for mammography images.

Corresponding metrics are listed below (parameter metric(s)).

Accuracy, Consistency

DATA SETS

Data source(s)

a) Specify the device(s) used to acquire the challenge data. This includes details on the device(s) used to acquire the imaging data (e.g. manufacturer) as well as information on additional devices used for performance assessment (e.g. tracking system used in a surgical setting).

Siemens Definition, Emotion, and Sensation scanner.

b) Describe relevant details on the imaging process/data acquisition for each acquisition device (e.g. image acquisition protocol(s)).

The thoracic CT scans are acquired under the protocol of Digital Imaging and Communications in Medicine (DICOM). The manual delineation of the airway is saved as the Neuroimaging Informatics Technology Initiative (NIFTI).

c) Specify the center(s)/institute(s) in which the data was acquired and/or the data providing platform/source (e.g. previous challenge). If this information is not provided (e.g. for anonymization reasons), specify why.

Same as ATM22.

[1] The thoracic CT scans of the BAS dataset are selected from the LIDC-IDRI dataset.

[2] Shanghai Chest Hospital

d) Describe relevant characteristics (e.g. level of expertise) of the subjects (e.g. surgeon)/objects (e.g. robot) involved in the data acquisition process (if any).

Each thoracic CT scan is first preprocessed by a strong deep learning model (Yu et.al) to acquire the preliminary labeling result and then delineated and double-checked by three radiologists with more than five years of professional experience to acquire the final refined airway tree labeling.

Yu W, et al, Tnn: Tree neural network for airway anatomical labeling. IEEE Transactions on Medical Imaging, 2022

Training and test case characteristics

a) State what is meant by one case in this challenge. A case encompasses all data that is processed to produce one result that is compared to the corresponding reference result (i.e. the desired algorithm output).

Examples:

- Training and test cases both represent a CT image of a human brain. Training cases have a weak annotation (tumor present or not and tumor volume (if any)) while the test cases are annotated with the tumor contour (if any).
- A case refers to all information that is available for one particular patient in a specific study. This information always includes the image information as specified in data source(s) (see above) and may include context information (see above). Both training and test cases are annotated with survival (binary) 5 years after (first) image was taken.

Training and test cases both represent a CT image of a human chest, They all have a full annotation of the airway tree labeling classes.

b) State the total number of training, validation and test cases.

Different from Task1, the manual annotation of fine-grained airway labeling is much more challenging. Therefore, the overall dataset is smaller than Task1.

The training dataset contains 128 CT scans, which are generally with the z-axis spacing smaller than 0.7mm and the quality of imaging is good without lesions. The test dataset contains 64 CT scans that can be categorized into three parts. The first part includes 32 CT scans generally with good image quality (z-axis spacing smaller than 0.7mm). The second part includes 16 CT scans that share large z-axis spacing. The third part contains 16 CT scans with low quality (e.g., with COVID-19 lesion). The second and the third parts correspond to these two tracks respectively, through which we can measure the robustness and the generalization ability of the automatic airway segmentation algorithms.

c) How much of the data are already annotated (stratified by train test in percentage)?

Full.

d) Explain why a total number of cases and the specific proportion of training, validation and test cases was chosen.

Same as Task 1.

e) Mention further important characteristics of the training, validation and test cases (e.g. class distribution in classification tasks chosen according to real-world distribution vs. equal class distribution) and justify the choice.

We mainly focus on the spacing of CT scans in training/validation/testing part. In this dataset, the CT scans in training dataset are generally with the z-axis spacing smaller than 0.7mm, and the quality of imaging is good without lesions. In testing part, we will add more samples with abnormal branching patterns.

f) Challenge organizers are encouraged to (partly) use unseen, unpublished data for their challenges. Describe if new data will be used for the challenge and state the number of cases along with the proportion of new data.

We use the same dataset as ATM22 while provide fine-grained airway labeling (lobular, segmental, subsegmental) annotations.

Annotation characteristics

a) Describe the method for determining the reference annotation, i.e. the desired algorithm output. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Possible methods include manual image annotation, in silico ground truth generation and annotation by automatic methods.

If human annotation was involved, state the number of annotators.

The airway tree labeling is manually annotated by three radiologists with more than five years of professional experience.

b) Provide the instructions given to the annotators (if any) prior to the annotation. This may include description of a training phase with the software. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Preferably, provide a link to the annotation protocol.

We follow the labeling paradigm in Zhang et.al and Li et.al. A generic multi-class pattern is defined in these works that the class of each airway branch can be determined by the location and the bi-furcation/tri-furcation properties. In this challenge, we only label the lobular/segmental/sub-segmental level annotation although there are several clinical studies to discover finer branching patterns. For more details, please refer to Zhang et.al which introduced detailed branching pattern distributions and variants of airways.

We implemented a new labeling software for radiologist. The software allows automatic branch splitting and load the pre-defined class names of airway labeling. Based on the groundtruth of airway segmentation, the radiologists used the software to determine the class of each branch.

Zhang et.al, AirMorph: Topology-Preserving Deep Learning for Pulmonary Airway Analysis, arxiv, 2024

Li et.al, Reflecting topology consistency and abnormality via learnable attentions for airway labeling, IJCARS 2025.

c) Provide details on the subject(s)/algorithm(s) that annotated the cases (e.g. information on level of expertise such as number of years of professional experience, medically-trained or not). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

They are radiologists with more than five years of professional experience.

d) Describe the method(s) used to merge multiple annotations for one case (if any). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

The radiologists are first label the cases independently without any discussion. After that, the groundtruth is obtained by the majority voting and confirmed by the senior radiologist.

Data pre-processing method(s)

Describe the method(s) used for pre-processing the raw training data before it is provided to the participating teams. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

The original thoracic CT scans share a large input size, while the airway tree structure exists in the lung area, hence, we provided the lung area coordinate (3D bounding box information) of each sample for localization usage.

Sources of error

a) Describe the most relevant possible error sources related to the image annotation. If possible, estimate the magnitude (range) of these errors, using inter-and intra-annotator variability, for example. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases, if necessary.

Restricted to the slice thickness and x-y plane resolution of CT scans, the distal small bronchus is hard to distinguish from the image level. We promise that our radiologists have dealt with such hard segmentation areas together and incorporated their professional experience as prior knowledge.

b) In an analogous manner, describe and quantify other relevant sources of error.

None.

ASSESSMENT METHODS

Metric(s)

a) Define the metric(s) to assess a property of an algorithm. These metrics should reflect the desired algorithm properties described in assessment aim(s) (see above). State which metric(s) were used to compute the ranking(s) (if any).

- Example 1: Dice Similarity Coefficient (DSC)

- Example 2: Area under curve (AUC)

- Branch-wise evaluation metrics are used: accuracy (ACC), and F1 score (F1).

- Additionally, two subtree-wise metrics were introduced: Subtree Consistency (SC), which evaluates the proportion of subtrees meeting anatomical labeling criteria, and Topological Distance (TD), which measures the shortest path length between predicted branches and their corresponding ground truth subtrees. The criteria for SC are:

1. Segmental Consistency: All nodes in a subtree share the same predicted segmental label.

2. Subsegmental Consistency: All nodes in a subtree share the same predicted segmental label and conform to the defined subsegmental topology, with nodes labeled as 'a', 'b', 'c', or bifurcation branches ('a+b', 'b+c', or 'a+c').

$$SC = Ncs/Ns,$$

where Ns is the total number of anatomical subtrees and Ncs is the number of consistently labeled subtrees.

Topological distance quantifies the average graph distance between predicted and ground-truth matched nodes:

$$TD = 1/N * \sum_{i=1}^N \min_{j \in \{j | y_j \neq \hat{y}_i\}} d(i,j)$$

where N is the total number of nodes in the airway graph, $d_{i,j}$ denotes the shortest path length between node v_i and node v_j , and y_j, \hat{y}_i represent the ground-truth and predicted labels, respectively.

- We build the hierarchy of the airway tree classes and calculate the class-to-class distance based on shortest distance in this hierarchy. The “near-miss” labeling error, termed as TAcc (TreeAcc) is measured by augmenting traditional accuracy metric with the weighted penalty based on the class-to-class distance above.

b) Justify why the metric(s) was/were chosen, preferably with reference to the biomedical application.

Airway tree labeling is a classification task. The aim is to determine the fine-grained labels of each airway branch. Therefore, we first use the generic metrics for classification. Besides, airway is a tree-like structure. It is also important to measure the hierarchical consistency which is very important for tree-like anatomies.

To help the readers and participants understand the error sources, we will also report the binary segmentation error which is not considered in ranking. According to previous works, the multi-class labeling of airway tree can be solved by two paradigms:

[1]End-to-end Multi-Class Segmentation: This is similar to multi-class segmentation tasks which directly generates the voxel-wise class labels based on unified neural network. We will report the binary segmentation accuracy by treating all foreground voxels of the prediction to the same class.

[2]Multi-Stage Methods: Previous works also adopted the multi-staged pipeline that first generates the binary segmentation of airway region, followed by the skeleton extraction and classification. Since the binary segmentation result is required in this paradigm, we also report the binary accuracy of the airway segmentation.

Ranking method(s)

a) Describe the method used to compute a performance rank for all submitted algorithms based on the generated metric results on the test cases. Typically the text will describe how results obtained per case and metric are aggregated to arrive at a final score/ranking. Ideally, provide the ranking scheme as a concrete pseudo code.

Same as Task1.

b) Describe the method(s) used to manage submissions with missing results on test cases.

The standalone metrics are all suitable for this situation. If the submissions miss results, they will inevitably receive a low score.

c) Justify why the described ranking scheme(s) was/were used.

We consider both accuracy and tree-like consistency. Although previous works used the weighted score for ranking, we still prefer to the mean ranking position of each metrics as the final ranking. This is also widely used in recent challenges which can avoid the weighting issues and also achieves good agreements in our ATM22 without conflicts.

Statistical analyses

Provide an overview of the statistical approaches used in the scope of the challenge analysis. Details can be provided in the parameters below. For each parameter, justify why the described statistical method(s) was/were used and, if necessary, add a description of any method used to assess whether the data met the assumptions required for the particular statistical approach.

Same as Task 1.

Provide a description of how the precision of the performance estimates of individual algorithms is assessed (e.g. confidence interval of the mean on the test set computed using percentile bootstrap, confidence interval of the accuracy on the test set computed using percentile bootstrap).

Same as Task 1.

Provide a description of how variability of the performance of individual algorithms across tests cases is assessed (e.g. SD across test cases, IQR, graphs, reporting outliers...).

Per-generation distributions; confusion matrices; rare label performance reporting.

Provide a description of how variability of rankings is assessed.

Same as Task 1.

Provide a description of statistical tests that are used to assess whether the differences in performance between algorithms are statistically significant.

Same as Task 1.

Provide a description of the missing data handling.

Same as Task 1.

Indicate any software product that is used for all data analysis methods.

Same as Task 1.

Further analyses

Present further analyses to be performed (if applicable), e.g. related to

- combining algorithms via ensembling,
- inter-algorithm variability,
- common problems/biases of the submitted methods, or
- ranking variability.

Same as Task 1.

TASK 3: Landmark Recognition for Endobronchial Intervention

SUMMARY

Abstract

Provide a summary of the challenge purpose. This should include a general introduction in the topic from both a biomedical as well as from a technical point of view and clearly state the envisioned technical and/or biomedical impact of the challenge.

ATM26 Task 3 targets visionbased bronchoscopy navigation. Given monocular bronchoscopy video (optionally with CT priors), participants estimate bronchoscope localization with branch-wise labeling names (e.g. RB6, LB7a).

Keywords

List the primary keywords that characterize the task.

bronchoscopy navigation, visual localization

ORGANIZATION

Organizers

a) Provide information on the organizing team (names and affiliations).

Same as Task1

b) Provide information on the primary contact person.

Yun Gu (yungu@ieee.org), Junyang Wu (sjtu_wjy@sjtu.edu.cn)

c) Indicate whether clinicians are part of the organizing team. If yes, describe their role.

Same as Task 1.

Life cycle type

Define the intended submission cycle of the challenge. Include information on whether/how the challenge will be continued after the challenge has taken place. Not every challenge closes after the submission deadline (one-time event). Sometimes it is possible to submit results after the deadline (open call) or the challenge is repeated with some modifications (repeated event).

Examples:

- One-time event with fixed conference submission deadline
- Open call (challenge opens for new submissions after conference deadline)
- Repeated event with annual fixed conference submission deadline

Repeated event with annual fixed conference submission deadline

Challenge venue and platform

a) Report the event (e.g. conference) that is associated with the challenge (if any).

MICCAI 2026

b) Report the platform used to run the challenge.

grand-challenge.org

c) Do you agree that the your submission is shared with the platform (e.g., grand-challenge, synapse...) that you indicated?

Please note: 1) this purpose of such sharing is that the challenge chairs and the platform can communicate smoothly, your answer won't impact the review of your proposal; 2) regardless of your response to this question, it is your responsibility to perform all actions required by the platform (e.g. filling their submission request).

Yes

d) Provide the URL for the challenge website (if any).

<https://atm26.grand-challenge.org/> (to appear)

Participation policies

a) Define the allowed user interaction of the algorithms assessed. This includes the policy regarding any curation, (pre-)processing and (pre-)training steps.

Fully automatic inference only; no human-in-the-loop correction on test sequences.

b) Define the policy on the usage of training data. The data used to train algorithms may, for example, be restricted to the data provided by the challenge or may also include publicly available data including (open) pre-trained nets. Clarify whether such additional data needs to be publicly available at the time of the challenge launch. Clarify whether adding (private) annotations of the public data is allowed.

Same as Task1.

c) Define the participation policy for members of the organizers' institutes. For example, members of the organizers' institutes may participate in the challenge but are not eligible for awards.

May participate but not eligible for awards and not listed in leaderboard

d) Define the award policy. In particular, provide details with respect to challenge prizes.

best overall Task 3

e) Define the policy for result announcement.

Examples:

- Top 3 performing methods will be announced publicly.
- Participating teams can choose whether the performance results will be made public.

Same as Task 1.

f) Define the publication policy. In particular, provide details on ...

- ... who of the participating teams/the participating teams' members qualifies as author
- ... whether the participating teams may publish their own results separately, and (if so)

- ... whether an embargo time is defined (so that challenge organizers can publish a challenge paper first).

Same as Task 1.

Submission method

a) Describe the method used for result submission. Preferably, provide a link to the submission instructions.

Examples:

- Docker container on the Synapse platform. Link to submission instructions: <URL>
- Algorithm output was sent to organizers via e-mail. Submission instructions were sent by e-mail.

Docker container submission. Input: Endoscopic frames. Output: multi-class label .

b) Provide information on the possibility for participating teams to evaluate their algorithms before submitting final results. For example, many challenges allow submission of multiple results, and only the last run is officially counted to compute challenge results.

Yes. Validation evaluation server with submission limits; local evaluation kit provided. The validation platform is a docker with 2*RTX3090 GPU (48GB VRAM)

Challenge schedule

Provide a timetable for the challenge. Preferably, this should include

- the release date(s) of the training cases (if any)
- the registration date/period
- the release date(s) of the test cases and validation cases (if any)
- the submission date(s)
- associated workshop days (if any)
- the release date(s) of the results

Same as Task 1.

Ethics approval

Indicate whether ethics approval is necessary for the data. If yes, provide details on the ethics approval, preferably institutional review board, location, date and number of the ethics approval (if applicable). Add the URL or a reference to the document of the ethics approval (if available).

Same as Task 1.

Data usage agreement

Clarify how the data can be used and distributed by the teams that participate in the challenge and by others during and after the challenge. This should include the explicit listing of the license applied.

Examples:

- CC BY (Attribution)

- CC BY-SA (Attribution-ShareAlike)
- CC BY-ND (Attribution-NoDerivs)
- CC BY-NC (Attribution-NonCommercial)
- CC BY-NC-SA (Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike)
- CC BY-NC-ND (Attribution-NonCommercial-NoDerivs)

Please note that the data license should not differ among sources. In case a license has to be changed, it has to be reported to the MICCAI challenges team and changed in the proposal.

CC BY-NC-SA (Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike)

Code availability

a) Provide information on the accessibility of the organizers' evaluation software (e.g. code to produce rankings). Preferably, provide a link to the code and add information on the supported platforms.

Same as Task 1.

b) In an analogous manner, provide information on the accessibility of the participating teams' code.

Same as Task1.

Conflicts of interest

Provide information related to conflicts of interest. In particular provide information related to sponsoring/funding of the challenge. Also, state explicitly who had/will have access to the test case labels and when.

Same as Task 1.

MISSION OF THE CHALLENGE

Field(s) of application

State the main field(s) of application that the participating algorithms target.

Examples:

- Diagnosis
- Education
- Intervention assistance
- Intervention follow-up
- Intervention planning
- Prognosis
- Research
- Screening
- Training
- Cross-phase

Assistance, Intervention planning

Task category(ies)

State the task category(ies)

Examples:

- Classification
- Detection
- Localization
- Modeling
- Prediction
- Reconstruction
- Registration
- Retrieval
- Segmentation
- Tracking

Classification, Localization, Tracking

Cohorts

We distinguish between the target cohort and the challenge cohort. For example, a challenge could be designed around the task of medical instrument tracking in robotic kidney surgery. While the challenge could be based on ex vivo data obtained from a laparoscopic training environment with porcine organs (challenge cohort), the final biomedical application (i.e. robotic kidney surgery) would be targeted on real patients with certain characteristics defined by inclusion criteria such as restrictions regarding sex or age (target cohort).

a) Describe the target cohort, i.e. the subjects/objects from whom/which the data would be acquired in the final biomedical application.

Same as Task 1.

b) Describe the challenge cohort, i.e. the subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the challenge data was acquired.

1. Samples from Shanghai Chest Hospital from 15 patients who underwent endobronchial intervention during 2019.1 and 2020.1.

Imaging modality(ies)

Specify the imaging technique(s) applied in the challenge.

Endoscope. It should be noted that fluoroscopy and CBCT are widely used for guidance. However, they are radiation imaging which may increase the risk for surgeons. Recent works on pure-vision methods, only using the bronchoscopy videos or ultrasound, are widely investigated and developing rapidly. They are friendly to surgeons while the navigation performance and effectiveness still require further improvement. This motivates us to organise the ATM26 challenge. Our vision is to improve current endobronchial intervention with better guidance

solutions and radiation-free imaging.

Context information

Provide additional information given along with the images. The information may correspond ...

a) ... directly to the image data (e.g. tumor volume).

None.

b) ... to the patient in general (e.g. sex, medical history).

Same as Task 1.

Target entity(ies)

a) Describe the data origin, i.e. the region(s)/part(s) of subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the image data would be acquired in the final biomedical application (e.g. brain shown in computed tomography (CT) data, abdomen shown in laparoscopic video data, operating room shown in video data, thorax shown in fluoroscopy video). If necessary, differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

Lumen shown in Endobronchial videos.

b) Describe the algorithm target, i.e. the structure(s)/subject(s)/object(s)/component(s) that the participating algorithms have been designed to focus on (e.g. tumor in the brain, tip of a medical instrument, nurse in an operating theater, catheter in a fluoroscopy scan). If necessary, differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

Same as Task 1.

Assessment aim(s)

Identify the property(ies) of the algorithms to be optimized to perform well in the challenge. If multiple properties are assessed, prioritize them (if appropriate). The properties should then be reflected in the metrics applied (see below, parameter metric(s)), and the priorities should be reflected in the ranking when combining multiple metrics that assess different properties.

- Example 1: Find highly accurate liver segmentation algorithm for CT images.
- Example 2: Find lung tumor detection algorithm with high sensitivity and specificity for mammography images.

Corresponding metrics are listed below (parameter metric(s)).

Accuracy,Consistency

DATA SETS

Data source(s)

a) Specify the device(s) used to acquire the challenge data. This includes details on the device(s) used to acquire the imaging data (e.g. manufacturer) as well as information on additional devices used for performance assessment (e.g. tracking system used in a surgical setting).

Olympus P290, XP290 and Pentax bronchoscopes .

b) Describe relevant details on the imaging process/data acquisition for each acquisition device (e.g. image acquisition protocol(s)).

The endobronchial videos are captured by the video stacks of endoscope manufacturers, which are then split to frames. The manual labeling of landmark is save as JSON files.

c) Specify the center(s)/institute(s) in which the data was acquired and/or the data providing platform/source (e.g. previous challenge). If this information is not provided (e.g. for anonymization reasons), specify why.

Shanghai Chest Hospital

d) Describe relevant characteristics (e.g. level of expertise) of the subjects (e.g. surgeon)/objects (e.g. robot) involved in the data acquisition process (if any).

Three surgeons with more than five years of professional experience to acquire the final landmarks.

Li et al, Development and validation of the artificial intelligence (AI)-based diagnostic model for bronchial lumen identification, Translational Lung Cancer Research, 2022

Training and test case characteristics

a) State what is meant by one case in this challenge. A case encompasses all data that is processed to produce one result that is compared to the corresponding reference result (i.e. the desired algorithm output).

Examples:

- Training and test cases both represent a CT image of a human brain. Training cases have a weak annotation (tumor present or not and tumor volume (if any)) while the test cases are annotated with the tumor contour (if any).
- A case refers to all information that is available for one particular patient in a specific study. This information always includes the image information as specified in data source(s) (see above) and may include context information (see above). Both training and test cases are annotated with survival (binary) 5 years after (first) image was taken.

Training and test cases both represent an endobronchial video of a human chest, They all have a full annotation of the per-frame landmark class.

b) State the total number of training, validation and test cases.

The training dataset contains 15 videos with 15,000 frames in total and 5 videos for validation (5,000 frames) The test dataset contains 10 videos with 10,000 frames in total. Compared to the training dataset which are generally clean, the test set will introduce more frames with strong artefacts. The frames which are severely blurred or the endtip of the bronchoscopy is touching the lumen wall (e.g. no lumen can be seen) are not included in the dataset. We also provide the CT scans for all patients.

c) How much of the data are already annotated (stratified by train test in percentage)?

67% since we plan to extend the dataset compared with the original proposal.

d) Explain why a total number of cases and the specific proportion of training, validation and test cases was chosen.

Same as Task 1.

e) Mention further important characteristics of the training, validation and test cases (e.g. class distribution in classification tasks chosen according to real-world distribution vs. equal class distribution) and justify the choice.

There is no specific focus of the video data. The only difference is that we will add more sample with strong artefacts (blur, blood) to the testing set. The frames which are severely blurred or the endtip of the bronchoscopy is touching the lumen wall (e.g. no lumen can be seen) are not included in the dataset.

f) Challenge organizers are encouraged to (partly) use unseen, unpublished data for their challenges. Describe if new data will be used for the challenge and state the number of cases along with the proportion of new data.

This is the new dataset which has not been published.

Annotation characteristics

a) Describe the method for determining the reference annotation, i.e. the desired algorithm output. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Possible methods include manual image annotation, in silico ground truth generation and annotation by automatic methods.

If human annotation was involved, state the number of annotators.

The landmark is manually annotated by three surgeons with more than five years of professional experience.

b) Provide the instructions given to the annotators (if any) prior to the annotation. This may include description of a training phase with the software. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Preferably, provide a link to the annotation protocol.

The labels of brochscopy video frames are acquired by manually aligning the intra-operative endobronchial views to the preoperative virtual endoscopic views, which can be automatically rendered by setting specific virtual camera in pulmonary airway. Since the groundtruth of airway branches can be obtained by Task2, we therefore obtain the label of bronchoscopy frames based on the real-to-virtual alignment. We follow Taylor et.al to use a registration method for rough alignment which is further refined by manual check. TWe implemented a new labeling software. The surgeons used the software to determine the class of each video frame.

Taylor et.al, Colonoscopy 3D video dataset with paired depth from 2D-3D registration, MIA 2023

c) Provide details on the subject(s)/algorithm(s) that annotated the cases (e.g. information on level of expertise such as number of years of professional experience, medically-trained or not). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

They are surgeons with more than five years of professional experience.

d) Describe the method(s) used to merge multiple annotations for one case (if any). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

The surgeons are first label the cases independently without any discussion. After that, the groundtruth is obtained by the majority voting and confirmed by the senior surgeon.

Data pre-processing method(s)

Describe the method(s) used for pre-processing the raw training data before it is provided to the participating teams. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

There is no specific pre-processing of the video frames.

Sources of error

a) Describe the most relevant possible error sources related to the image annotation. If possible, estimate the magnitude (range) of these errors, using inter-and intra-annotator variability, for example. Provide the information

separately for the training, validation and test cases, if necessary.

Due to the motion bluriness and the artefacts, the accurate recognition of landmark can be very challenging. However, we promise that the surgeons will refer to the preoperative CT scans and temporal consistency to double check.

b) In an analogous manner, describe and quantify other relevant sources of error.

None.

ASSESSMENT METHODS

Metric(s)

a) Define the metric(s) to assess a property of an algorithm. These metrics should reflect the desired algorithm properties described in assessment aim(s) (see above). State which metric(s) were used to compute the ranking(s) (if any).

- Example 1: Dice Similarity Coefficient (DSC)
- Example 2: Area under curve (AUC)

- Macro-F1 and accuracy (ACC) per frame.

- The Edit Score is computed using the Levenshtein distance e , which quantifies how similar two sequences X, Y are to each other by counting the minimum number of operations required to convert one (segment) string into another.

$$\text{Edit} = 1 - \frac{e(X, Y)}{\max(|X|, |Y|)} \cdot 100$$

- We also report the TAcc following the same protocol in Task2.

b) Justify why the metric(s) was/were chosen, preferably with reference to the biomedical application.

The landmark recognition based on video frames is a classification task. Therefore, we use the metrics for classification is this task. The edit score is to measure the temporal consistency. TAcc is to address the “near-missing” cases based on airway label hierachy.

Ranking method(s)

a) Describe the method used to compute a performance rank for all submitted algorithms based on the generated metric results on the test cases. Typically the text will describe how results obtained per case and metric are aggregated to arrive at a final score/ranking. Ideally, provide the ranking scheme as a concrete pseudo code.

Same as Task1.

b) Describe the method(s) used to manage submissions with missing results on test cases.

The standalone metrics are all suitable for this situation. If the submissions miss results, they will inevitably receive a low score.

c) Justify why the described ranking scheme(s) was/were used.

Although previous works used the weighted score for ranking, we still prefer to the mean ranking position of each metrics as the final ranking. This is also widely used in recent challenges which can avoid the weighting issues and also achieves good agreements in our ATM22 without conflicts.

Statistical analyses

Provide an overview of the statistical approaches used in the scope of the challenge analysis. Details can be provided in the parameters below. For each parameter, justify why the described statistical method(s) was/were used and, if necessary, add a description of any method used to assess whether the data met the assumptions required for the particular statistical approach.

Same as Task 1.

Provide a description of how the precision of the performance estimates of individual algorithms is assessed (e.g. confidence interval of the mean on the test set computed using percentile bootstrap, confidence interval of the accuracy on the test set computed using percentile bootstrap).

Same as Task 1.

Provide a description of how variability of the performance of individual algorithms across tests cases is assessed (e.g. SD across test cases, IQR, graphs, reporting outliers...).

Error over time; drift vs time; artifact-correlated failure analysis.

Provide a description of how variability of rankings is assessed.

Same as Task 1.

Provide a description of statistical tests that are used to assess whether the differences in performance between algorithms are statistically significant.

Same as Task 1.

Provide a description of the missing data handling.

Same as Task 1.

Indicate any software product that is used for all data analysis methods.

Same as Task 1.

Further analyses

Present further analyses to be performed (if applicable), e.g. related to

- combining algorithms via ensembling,
- inter-algorithm variability,
- common problems/biases of the submitted methods, or
- ranking variability.

Same as Task 1.

ADDITIONAL POINTS

References

Please include any reference important for the challenge design, for example publications on the data, the annotation process or the chosen metrics as well as DOIs referring to data or code.

Zhang et al, Multi-site, multi-domain airway tree modeling, Medical Image Analysis, 2023

Further comments

Further comments from the organizers.

N/A